

WAERMER

Waermewende im urbanen Gebäudebestand mit Hilfe interaktiver Entscheidungsraumanalyse

**Changing One's Heating System?
Quantitative and Qualitative Study Among Homeowners**

Deliverable 2.6

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Johanna Holzberg & Andreas Ernst

Center for Environmental Systems Research, Universität Kassel

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Overview

In addition to the qualitative and quantitative survey and interview study conducted in the city of Kiel, the same approach was used to investigate homeowners' perceptions in another city of Germany. Therefore, Kassel was selected to carry out the study. A district was chosen that shared similarities with the districts that had been investigated in Kiel. It consisted of freestanding single-family houses, semi-detached houses, or row houses. The survey was adapted (for a detailed description, see Chapter 2) to reflect the current situation regarding price changes and political developments. Flyers were designed and distributed in the selected districts. For the data analysis for the quantitative data R Studio was used, for the transcription of the interviews Whisper (OpenAI, 2023) was used locally and the resulting transcripts were analyzed using MAXQDA (VERBI Software GmbH, 2024). In the questionnaire study participants were asked to rate three different heating scenarios considering different aspects, and to state their intention to install such a heating system. In the interviews, the focus was more on the individual household, exploring homeowners' perceptions of different systems, their concerns, barriers, and opinions.

1. Sample recruitment and description

A flyer was designed containing information about the survey, what it entails, as well as a QR code to the link and the link itself. Additionally, it was mentioned that an interview was also possible, including the contact information for scheduling one. The flyers were distributed in November 2025 in the chosen district of Kassel. Data collection for both studies took place from 1 November 2025 to 31 January 2026. For the survey, 42 datasets were suitable for further analysis. For the Interviews, only three datasets were successfully obtained. Therefore, no further information about the gender or age of the three participants is reported to maintain data anonymity. Moreover, the results from the interviews are reported in a general manner to ensure that no individual can be identified.

For the quantitative study, the age distribution is shown in Figure 1. Most participants were older than 50 years. Thirty-four participants stated being female, seven participants being male, and one participant did not wish to disclose their gender. No participant reported identifying as non-binary. The distribution of the income groups is shown in Figure 2. Thirteen Participants stated having a monthly net household income above €5.500, nine an income of over €4.400 to €5.500, and 13 reported an income of €3.300 to €4.400.

Figure 1: Age distribution in the quantitative study

Figure 2: Income distribution in the quantitative study

2. Methods

For the quantitative study, the same online survey as in the project's first quantitative study from 2023 was used (for more detailed information, see Holzberg & Ernst, 2025). The questionnaire was conducted using Soci Survey (Leiner, 2023). For the qualitative interview study, the interview manual from the previous interview study was used as well. In both cases (qualitative and quantitative studies), the materials were slightly adapted to the current situation. The materials and the adaptations are described in more detail in the following sections.

2.1. Materials

For the quantitative survey study, the questionnaire from our survey study in Kiel was used (Holzberg & Ernst, 2025). In order to adapt to the current context of data collection, the questionnaire was revised. Some items were excluded from the survey. These were questions that specifically asked for the amount of electricity used or the amount of the energy source consumed. Additionally, the capacity of the PV system was no longer requested. This was done to reduce the time and effort required from participants to take part in the study. Furthermore, the scenarios were updated to reflect current pricing. As a result, participants had to read the following text in the survey (translated to English):

You have various options for heating your residential building and for preparing hot water. On the following pages, we describe three selected heat technologies for you. Please imagine how appealing you find these technologies in your current living situation. Although modern heating systems are expensive to purchase and install, the resulting costs can be significantly reduced through appropriate funding programs, and they lead to savings in long-term cost compared to conventional systems.

Please read through the following scenarios and evaluate them for yourself. Only your personal opinion matters here—there is no right or wrong answer.

Please note that the investment cost figures provided for all scenarios are estimated guideline values. These are not fixed and may be lower or higher depending on the overall supply

situation, local price levels, and the structural characteristics of the respective buildings and properties.

After these instructions and introduction, the following three scenarios were presented to the participants (randomized).

Scenario 1:

The costs for maintaining a gas boiler amount to approximately €20,000. These are referred to as "inevitable" costs. They include acquisition, installation, maintenance, heating load, and repairs over a period of 20 years. Please note that all cost figures provided are estimated guideline values. These are not fixed and may be lower or higher depending on the overall supply situation, local price levels, and the structural characteristics of the respective buildings and properties.

Heat pump in combination with a photovoltaic system

One option is replacing your currently installed heating system with a heat pump (€40,000) and a photovoltaic system for a medium-sized roof (7.2 kWp, 16 modules, €20,000). After deducting the state basic subsidy of 30% for the heat pump and without any deduction for the PV system, the total cost would be €48,000. These figures represent the costs for a typical installation based on full-cost calculation. Modern heat pumps are highly efficient and produce two up to, in some cases, five times more useful heat from outside air, ground heat, or groundwater than the electrical energy they consume. When a heat pump is combined with a sufficiently powerful photovoltaic system, the ongoing operating costs for heating your residential building and producing hot water can be significantly reduced. Furthermore, this combined solution ensures a high degree of independence from the energy market. This allows you to heat your building almost without climate-harming CO₂ emissions.

Scenario 2:

The costs for maintaining a gas boiler amount to approximately €20,000. The costs for maintaining a gas boiler amount to approximately €20,000. These are referred to as "inevitable" costs. They include acquisition, installation, maintenance, heating load, and repairs over a period of 20 years. Please note that all cost figures provided are estimated guideline values. These are not fixed and may be lower or higher depending on the overall supply situation, local price levels, and the structural characteristics of the respective buildings and properties.

Shared purchase and operation of a heat pump in combination with a photovoltaic system

One option is replacing your currently installed heating system with a larger heat pump and photovoltaic system that are jointly acquired and operated by several neighbours. Even after deducting state funding, the cost for one household would be €35,000 for a typical system, for example, serving five houses (a total of €175,000 for all together). The remaining costs would be shared among the neighbours. Modern heat pumps are highly efficient and produce two up to, in some cases, five times more useful heat from outside air, ground heat, or groundwater than the electrical energy they consume. When a larger heat pump is combined with a

sufficiently powerful photovoltaic system, the ongoing operating costs for heating your residential building and producing hot water can be significantly reduced. Furthermore, this combined solution ensures a high degree of independence from the energy market. This allows you to heat your building almost without climate-damaging CO₂ emissions.

Scenario 3:

The costs for maintaining a gas boiler amount to approximately €20,000. These are referred to as "inevitable" costs. They include acquisition, installation, maintenance, heating load, and repairs over a period of 20 years. Please note that all cost figures provided are estimated guideline values. These are not fixed and may be lower or higher depending on the overall supply situation, local price levels, and the structural characteristics of the respective buildings and properties. No statements are made regarding whether connection to a district heating grid is possible or planned in your local area.

Connection to the local district heating grid

One option may be replacing your currently installed heating system with a connection to a district heating grid. The costs for a typical installation in Germany range from approximately €10,000 to €15,000. Depending on the region and specific conditions, additional funding may be available.

A so-called district heating interface station will be installed in the building, requiring little space and providing you with hot water ready for use. Maintenance and repair costs typical for other heating systems do not apply to a district heating connection, as they are already included in the base tariff. Operation requires no further action from the household occupants. Central heating plants generate the necessary energy and feed hot water into the district heating grid. If a gas-fired power plant is used to produce the heat, slightly fewer climate-damaging CO₂ emissions are released compared to a conventional central heating system.

For each of those three scenarios, participants were asked to rate the described heating system regarding different aspects, which were also selected based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB; Ajzen, 1991). This includes items related to the participant's attitude toward the system, how they perceive their peers' evaluation of the system, how important they consider this opinion, and how capable they feel regarding the financial costs and construction work associated with the system. The items used in the survey and their classification according to the TPB are shown in Table 1. Additionally, participants were asked to rate their willingness to install the system—either within the next five years or whether they could imagine installing such a heating system in general.

Table 1: Items for scenario ratings and their TPB categories

Item	TPB
The heating method presented...	
... I consider environmentally friendly	Attitude
... I consider cost-effective in operation	Attitude
... I consider to be a reliable solution	Attitude

... I think is worth striving for	Attitude
... would my neighbours approve of.	Social Norms
... my friends/my family would approve of	Social Norms
The opinion of my neighbours on this matter is important to me.	Social Norms
The opinion of my friends/my family on this matter is important to me.	Social Norms
... I consider feasible for installation in my house	Perceived behaviour control
... I consider financially feasible for implementation in my home	Perceived behaviour control

For the qualitative study, the interview manual (see Appendix 1 for the manual in German) was also adapted. There was one question on the share of renewable energy sources a heating system would need to utilize, if communal planning were implemented and a system had to be changed. It had to be removed due to the change in government, as the new government announced its intention to abolish and revise the heating law.

2.2. Analysis

To analyze the data from the quantitative data collection R (R Core Team, 2023) and RStudio (Posit Team, 2023) were used. To predict participants' *Installation Intention* and investigate important factors that may influence it, regression models were calculated based on 18 predictors. The predictors included sociodemographic variables (such as *Gender*, *Income*, or *Education*), environmental concerns, sources of information, and knowledge. The regression analysis that was used for the regression model selection is called best-subset selection and is performed using *dredge* which is part of the package *MuMin* (Multi-Model Inference; Bartoń, 2023) in RStudio. This method calculates every possible model based on the given predictors and selects the model that best fits data. Since p-values are not recommended for interpretation when using this kind of model selection, a commonality analysis (using the package *yhat*; Nimon, Oswald & Roberts, 2021) was conducted based on the final regression model. This allows for an indication of which predictors have a greater impact on the dependent variable, installation intention, compared to other predictors in the model. A regression model and commonality analysis were calculated for each scenario. In this process, the predictors based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) were treated as fixed predictors, meaning they were intended to be included in every final regression model.

Due to a very low response rate for the interviews in Kassel (only three interviews took place), and to maintain anonymity when reporting the results, the different categories conducted for the interview study described in Holzberg and Ernst (2026) are not presented in detail. Only a broad description of the reasons mentioned for or against a change, as well as the positive or negative aspects mentioned regarding different heating systems, is provided here.

3. Results

3.1. Quantitative Data

The results for the regression models are shown in Table 2. For Scenario 1 (installing a heat pump in combination with a photovoltaic system), 37 datasets were used for the regression model. The regression model has an adjusted R^2 of 0.74, indicating that 74% of the variance in the dependent variable, installation intention, can be explained by the proposed model.

Table 2: Regression models for *Installation Intention* for the three Scenarios in Kassel

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
	Heat pump and PV	Heat pump and PV with neighbours	Connection to a heating grid
N	37	40	40
R ²	0.83	0.38	0.62
Adjusted R ²	0.74	0.29	0.52
Predictors	Coefficients (SE)	Coefficients (SE)	Coefficients (SE)
Constant	-96.36 (20.39)	-8.79 (11.90)	3.73 (15.40)
Attitudes	0.29 (0.19)	0.33 (0.19)	0.38 (0.17)
Social Norm	-0.28 (0.14)	-0.12 (0.14)	-0.29 (0.16)
Perceived Behaviour Control	0.23 (0.15)	-0.01 (0.11)	0.16 (0.10)
Knowledge	1.15 (3.32)	0.60 (0.16)	0.77 (0.16)
No responsibility for heating system	0.614 (0.14)		
Knowledge about heat pumps	-13.73 (3.13)	-8.90 (3.39)	-9.07 (3.37)
Independence from neighbours	0.21 (0.09)		
Education_vocational training	41.57 (20.12)		
E_university entrance qualification	45.52 (11.44)		
E_master training school	68.32 (19.55)		
E_University of Applied Sciences	12.7 (10.32)		
E_University Degree	6.91 (10.33)		
Source of Knowledge			-0.54 (0.20)
Number of heat pumps in social network			-6.44 (2.73)
Finances			0.61 (0.19)

Notes: The predictor Education (E) is dummy coded. The categories 1 and 2 (*no school leaving certificate* and *secondary school certificate*) were not present in the data. Therefore, the reference category 3 is *intermediate school leaving certificate*

Next to the predictors based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), important predictors for *Installation Intention* are *Knowledge*, *No responsibility for heating systems*, *Knowledge about heat pumps*, *Independence from neighbours*, and *Education*. The predictor *Knowledge* includes the following items: "Information about funding opportunities for other systems has sparked my interest in them", "I feel well-informed about the various possible heating technologies" and "I feel well-informed about the financial funding available for the installation of certain heating systems.". *No responsibility for heating systems* is formed through the items "With a heating system, I would like to have to take care of it as little as possible during operation" and "When installing a new heating system, I would like to have to worry about details as little as possible". *Knowledge about heat pumps* is a predictor where the participants were asked if they knew certain types of heat pumps (air-to-water heat pump, ground-source-heat pump, air-to-air heat pump). *Independence from neighbours* is the item "With regard to heating, it is important to me to be independent from my neighbours". The predictors *Social Norms* and *Knowledge about heat pumps* were both negatively connected to *Installation Intention*. For Scenario 2 (installing a heat pump in combination with a photovoltaic system together with neighbours) additional to the TPB predictors, *attitude*, *social norms* and *perceived behaviour control*, the predictors *Knowledge* and *Knowledge about heat pumps* were included in the model. The predictors *perceived behaviour control*, *Social Norms* and *Knowledge about heat pumps* all showed a negative association with *Installation Intention*.

For Scenario 3 (connection to a heating grid) in addition to the TPB predictors, *Knowledge* and *Knowledge about heat pumps* were also included. Other predictors that were included in the model are *Source of Knowledge*, *Finances* and *Number of heat pumps in social network*. The predictor *Source of knowledge* contains of the items:

"When choosing a new heating system ...

... I turn to a professional energy consultant"

... I turn to a heating installer."

... I compare several offers before hiring a tradesperson"

And "Before I make a decision on a heating technology,...

... I want to have understood how all the options work."

... I compare all options in terms of their investment and operating costs."

... I compare all options in terms of their environmental impacts."

... I compare all options in terms of the installation and operational effort required from me."

The predictor *Finances* includes items "When it comes to energy saving, cost savings are the top priority for my household" and "Due to rising energy prices, my household has to cut back on other expenses" and "The current rise in energy prices has prompted me to reconsider my current heating system".

The results from the commonality analysis are shown in Figure 3 (Scenario 1: heat pump and photovoltaic system), Figure 4 (Scenario 2: heat pump and photovoltaic system together with neighbours) and in Figure 5 (Scenario 3: connection to a heating grid). The commonality analysis shows how much variance from the R^2 can be contributed to each predictor of the regression model. For each predictor we see a blue, green, and orange bar. The blue bar (total effect) represents the total effect, meaning the unique and common effect combined. The green bar (unique effect) represents

Figure 3: Commonality Analysis Results for Scenario 1

Figure 4: Commonality Analysis Results for Scenario 2

Figure 5: Commonality Analysis Results for Scenario 3

the amount of variance that the predictor accounts for on its own. The orange bar (common effect) represents the variance that the predictor accounts for in combination with other predictors. For example, in Figure 3 the predictor *Knowledge* has the highest total effect, meaning that, of all the predictors in the model *Knowledge* contributes the most to the explained variance (of *Installation Intention*) of the regression model (R^2 , here 0.83). The unique effect of *Knowledge* is even higher, whereas the effect becomes negative when *Knowledge* is paired with the other predictors of the model. For Scenario 2, *Knowledge* is the most important factor for *Installation Intention* as well. For Scenario 3, *Knowledge* is the second most important factor after *Attitudes*.

3.1. Qualitative Data

As only three people participated in the interviews, the results will be presented broadly in order to maintain anonymity. Two participants rely solely on fossil-based heating systems; one has a hybrid system. All three participants have an additional photovoltaic system. Reasons against a system change that were mentioned include the belief that the house is not energy efficient enough, a reluctance to investigate the topic, and a desire not to have construction work carried out in the house.

Reasons for a change or for considering a change were environmental concerns, the failure of the old system, to enable a more energy efficient home and the fact that heating systems (here meaning heat pumps) have become technically advanced in recent years.

Regarding specific heating systems, negative aspects of the heat pump mentioned were a high noise level and aesthetic concerns. Positively it was noted that technology has improved. Uncertainty was expressed regarding how much electricity a heat pump would require and how electricity prices will develop in the future. For pellets, it was mentioned that no fossil fuels are used, but that they are not as environmentally favorable as other alternatives.

4. Discussion

The results indicate that in the district of Kassel, knowledge in some forms seems to play an important role in relation to homeowners' installation intentions. Since the survey is unable to distinguish the specific type of knowledge the participant is referring to, detailed interpretations cannot be made. The interviews were conducted to gather more information about the individual homeowner. However, since only three participants took part in the interviews, the role of knowledge could not be investigated further. However, knowledge may still be an interesting aspect that could be explored in future studies to identify which specific types of knowledge are relevant and whether this knowledge is accurate or based on misinformation. In Kiel (see Holzberg & Ernst, 2025), knowledge also played a role, but it was less prominent than perceived behavioral control, which had a more significant influence in the regression models. This could be explained by the fact that the sample in Kassel may be in a different state of knowledge compared to the sample from Kiel. Perhaps homeowners in Kiel had already engaged more with the practical aspects of how a system change could be implemented, rather than focusing on the information-seeking process.

In both cases, it must be emphasized that the samples are self-selected and likely biased. This means that most participants were probably already interested in the topic and had already thought about their heating systems and the possibility of a change.

In Kassel, the sample size, especially for the interviews, was quite small. This may be due to the fact that in Kiel, the city itself was actively involved in the district, and the flyers distributed included the city's logo. This may have increased the perceived seriousness of the study and built greater trust among homeowners. This was not the case in Kassel. Furthermore, in Kiel, the flyers were distributed twice, which likely contributed to a higher response rate.

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Appendix 1

Interview manual in German language

N	Leitfrage	Nachfrage(n)	Thema
1	Mit was für einem Heizsystem beheizen Sie aktuell ihr Haus?	Wie alt ist das System?	Status Quo, Zufriedenheit
2	Haben Sie eine Photovoltaik-Anlage oder Solarthermie?		
3	Sind Sie mit diesem zufrieden?	Ggf. nachfragen warum / warum nicht	
4	Sind Sie aktuell mit der Klimafreundlichkeit ihres Systems zufrieden?		
5	Haben Sie bereits darüber nachgedacht Ihr Heizsystem zu modernisieren?	Nein: Was wären Aspekte, die Sie über eine Modernisierung nachdenken lassen würde? Ja: Was hat Sie dazu bewogen?	Grund der Auseinandersetzung mit neuer Anlage
6	Mit welchen Heizsystemen haben Sie sich bisher beschäftigt? <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: 10px auto;">f) auch fragen, wenn bisher nicht mit neuem System beschäftigt</div>	Jedes System: a) Welche Nachteile sehen Sie in diesem System? b) Welche Vorteile sehen Sie bei diesem System? c) Haben Sie sich mit anderen über dieses System ausgetauscht? Gibt es weitere Quellen, die Sie nutzen oder genutzt haben, um sich über das System zu informieren? d) Gibt es Heizsysteme, welche Sie aus Klimaschutzgründen bevorzugen oder ausschließen würden? e) Weshalb haben Sie sich bisher gegen dieses System entschieden bzw. was hält sie aktuell davon ab? f) Bisher sind Heizsysteme, welche auf erneuerbaren Energien basieren in ihrer Anschaffung und Installation deutlich teurer als Gas- oder Ölheizungen. Wie stehen Sie vor diesem Hintergrund zu solchen erneuerbaren Heizsystemen? g) Fühlen Sie sich ausreichend über Fördermöglichkeiten für dieses System informiert? Was fehlt Ihnen? h) Wie empfinden Sie die Unterstützung der Politik? (bezogen auf Wärmeplanung, Fördermöglichkeiten, kommunale Wärmeplanung etc.)	Informationsgrad, persönliche Bewertung der Anlagen/Unterstützungen
7	Angenommen in ihrem Stadtteil würde es die Möglichkeit geben, sich an ein Nah- oder Fernwärmenetz anschließen zu lassen. Wäre es für Sie denkbar sich an ein solches Netz anschließen zu lassen?	Lieber als eine Individuelle Lösung?	Wärmenetze
8	Was halten Sie generell von Wärmepumpen?	Begründung	
9	Haben Sie bereits Erfahrungen mit einer Energieberatung oder mit Heizungsinstallateuren gemacht?	a) Wie empfanden Sie die Beratung? b) Ziehen Sie die Empfohlenen Maßnahmen in Betracht?	Professionelle Beratung

10	Zögern Sie aktuell, eine individuelle Lösung in Angriff zu nehmen, weil Sie abwarten möchten, wie die kommunale Wärmeplanung für ihren Stadtteil aussieht?		Verzögerung durch kommunale Planungen
11	Haben Sie das Gefühl, Sie hätten gerne weitere Informationen, bevor Sie sich um eine Heizungsmodernisierung kümmern können? Was für Informationen wünschen Sie sich?	Von wem sollten diese Informationen idealerweise kommen?	Wahrgenommene Unterstützung
12	Nach Abschluss der kommunalen Wärmeplanung sollen die Heizsysteme bei einem Austausch mit mindestens 65% erneuerbaren Energiequellen versorgt werden. Haben Sie bereits darüber nachgedacht, wie Sie dies in einem solchen Fall umsetzen wollen?		
13	Haben Sie noch Aspekte, welche Ihnen im Zusammenhang mit Heizsystemen besonders wichtig sind, und Ihrer Meinung nach noch zur Sprache gebracht werden sollten?		

Appendix 2

Packages used for data Analysis with R and RStudio

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